

Co-Benefits Indicators Used by Cohort 1 Mission Cities: Gap Analysis Report

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Table of Contents

1.0 Background	2
2.0 Co-benefit Indicators and Impact Pathways	2
3.0 Co-benefit Indicators: Locally Developed/Not Present	4
3.1 Co-benefit Indicators: Locally Developed/Not Present – Notes	11
3.2 Co-benefit Indicators: Too Generic for Subdomain Match	17
4.0 Recommendations	18
APPENDIX A – W1 Monitoring and Evaluation Tools & Indicators.....	19
APPENDIX B – W1 Mission Label Cities Co-benefits Factsheet Draft	22

1.0 Background

The following guidance documents¹ were produced by NZC to guide cities in the selection of co-benefit indicators as they developed their Climate City Contracts (CCCs). Of these, the NZC Theory of Change was adopted/operationalized in the CCCs in terms of how most of the co-benefit indicators were structured.

- NZC Theory of Change/Impact Pathways, available in various forms including in the [Pilot Cities Programme Guidebook](#), published June 2022
- Indicators for capital / finance needs and replication potential, published November 2023
- NZC Comprehensive Indicator Framework and Guidance, published March 2024

2.0 Co-benefit Indicators and Impact Pathways

To support understanding how cities are incorporating co-benefits indicators in their CCCs and facilitate future improvements to impact evaluation, a high-level analysis of the monitoring and evaluation components of Window 1 Mission Label Cities (see Appendix A) was conducted. A factsheet (see Appendix B) describing the co-benefits indicators used by the first cohort of Mission Label Cities was then developed. All 10 cities' CCCs were scanned for any mentions of co-benefits and indicators (see Table 1 below), and the data were extracted from the PDFs and consolidated in [this spreadsheet](#).

Table 1 Co-benefits Data in Climate City Contracts

City	Metadata?	Location in CCC
Cluj-Napoca	Yes	CD*, Section 2, p 8 (202); B-1.1, p 101-110; B-1.2, p 117; B-3.2, p 147-154; C.1.1, p 157-160; C-1.2, p 163-164; C.2.1, p 165-172
Klagenfurt	No	CD, Section 2, p 2 (40); B-1.1, p 12; C.1.1, p 30; C.2.1, p 30-31; C-3.1, p 31-33
Madrid	Yes	CD, 2030 climate neutrality target, p 11; B-1.1, p 61-67; B-3.2, p 89-129; C.1.1, p 130-132; C.1.1, p 134-136
Mannheim	No	CD, Section 2, p 3 (172) and Section 4, p 15 (184); B-1.1, p 52-53; B-2.2 indicators mentioned but co-benefits not specifically detailed
Sønderborg	No	CD, Introduction, p 2 (80) and Section 2 - Goal, p 8-9 (86-87); B-1.1, p 35-39; C.1.1, p 59; C.1.1, p 60-61; C-3.1, p 70
Stockholm	No	CD, Section 2, p 3 (50); B-1.1, p 30-32; C.1.1, p 41-42; C-3.1, p 44-45
Valencia	Yes	CD, Section 2, p 16; B-1.1, p 104-116; B-3.0-b, p 277-279; C.1.1, p 281-283; C.2.1, p 287-289; C-3, p 292-293; C-3.1, p 294-299
Valladolid	Yes	CD, Section 2, p 15; B-1.1, p 87-88; B-3.0, p 148-149; C.1.1, p 157-162; C.2.1, p 164-165
Vitoria-Gasteiz	Yes	CD, Section 2, p 12 (211); B-1.1, p 54-67; B-3.2, p 158-182; C-1.1, p 183-185; C.2.1, p 189-190; C-3.1, p 194-195
Zaragoza	No	CD, Section 2, p 13-14 and Section 3, p 17-18; B-1.1, p 71-73; C-1.1, p 75-76; C.2.1, p 77; C-3.1, p 79-81

*Commitments Document

Most of the indicators (712 in total) were concentrated in section B of the CCCs and conformed to the fields of climate action recommended. Apart from Cluj (who included innovation interventions in sections

¹ See [Impact pathways, Monitoring Evaluation and Learning framework and indicators](#) for more.

B & C), the co-benefits linked to innovation interventions (175 in total) were outlined in section C as per the CCC design and didn't follow the impact pathway logic. Therefore, the section B indicators were mapped onto the NZC Indicator Framework domains/sub-domains to assess the degree of conformity/divergence with the framework. Of the section B indicators, 296 (41%) had close/exact alignment with the NZC indicator system, 353 (50%) drew upon indicators from existing processes like the Green City Accord and other local processes (and/or were not present in NZC system), 63 (9%) didn't have enough information to specifically map to a NZC indicator system subdomain. The overall distribution by action field is given in Figure 1 below. The NZC indicator system domains are detailed below in Table 1 for ease of reference.

Table 2 NZC Indicator Framework – Recommended (voluntary) indicator domains

NZC Indicator Framework – Indicator Domains (Recommended)
Biodiversity
Digitalisation and Smart Urban Technology
Economy
Finance and Investment
Greenhouse Gas Emissions (GHG)
Public Health & Environment
Resource Efficiency
Social Inclusion, Innovation, Democracy and Cultural Impact

Figure 1 All Cohort 1 Impact Pathways

3.0 Co-benefit Indicators: Locally Developed/Not Present

During the mapping process, indicators were reviewed against the information in their impact pathways and the NZC Indicator Framework. Indicators were coded to the relevant NZC indicator domain and subdomain if it existed in relation to the indicator. Indicators that didn't have close/exact alignment with the framework were coded to the locally developed/not present in indicator system category.

Corresponding notes were written describing what these indicators measured and/or didn't cover, which are summarized in Section 3.1. These indicators are detailed by city in the frequency/action field tables that follow.

Table 3 Cluj-Napoca B-1.1 Indicators

Field(s) of Action	Indicator(s) Used	Frequency
Built Environment	Abate congestion from metropolitan commuting	1
	Improve performance of public sector employees and quality of public services	1
	Increased productivity of private sector due to better quality of working spaces	1
Built Environment	Reduce energy bills	1
Energy Systems	Reduce local budget energy costs	1
	Savings for local budget	1
Organisational and Governance	Lower energy costs for households	2
	Reduction of energy bills and CO2 emissions	1
Innovation		
Social and Other Innovation	Energy cost reduction for households	1
Built Environment	Potentially generate additional sources of revenue from energy generation	1
Energy Systems		
Built Environment	Reduce flight to suburbs, by improving quality of life in existing neighborhoods	1
Green infrastructure & nature-based solutions	Reduce flight to suburbs by improving quality of living spaces in existing neighborhoods	1
Mobility & Transport	Reduce flight to suburbs by making existing neighborhoods more attractive	1
Energy Systems	Increased safety of public spaces	1
Energy Systems	Improved quality of life	5
Mobility & Transport	Improved wellness and quality of life of residents	1
Waste & circular economy		
Green infrastructure & nature-based solutions	Encourage more trips by foot & green transport modes	1
	Make commuting by bike and green micro-mobility options more attractive	1
Green infrastructure & nature based solutions	Reduced congestion	4
Mobility & Transport		
Social and Other Innovation	Reduced urban sprawl	1

Mobility & Transport	Make public spaces safer for children, elderly, and people with disabilities	1
	More affordable transport by car	1
Organisational and Governance Innovation	Behavioural change fostered via transparent & accessible communication	1
	Capacitated local ecosystem	1
	Condominiums earn a central role in implementing any climate neutrality policies at neighborhood level	1
	Cost of interventions is significantly reduced	1
	Creative financing options are tapped	1
	Improved effectiveness/efficiency of multilevel governance for climate neutrality	1
	Improved learning process and related outcomes	1
	Institutionalised systems for implementation and monitoring of climate neutral policies	1
	Rehabilitation of existing stock is completed much faster	1
	Stronger local commitment/ownership of climate neutrality objectives	1
Social and Other Innovation	Unlocked favourable systemic conditions for climate neutrality	1
	Evidence-based substantiation of climate neutrality interventions	1
	Increased innovation and technological progress	1
	Innovative, data-based decision making process	1
	Real time adjustments to the proposals made, based on changing circumstances	1
	Rehabilitated existing housing stock	1

Table 4 Klagenfurt B-1.1 Indicators

Field(s) of Action	Indicator(s) Used	Frequency
Built Environment	Less social tensions as sustainable housing is not a luxury, but a possibility for all social groups	1
	Society sees sustainable housing as the new standard	1
	Sustainable new houses have become the new standard	1
	Thanks to continuous learning processes, renovation processes gain on quality and new sustainable housing approaches can be developed	1
	Thanks to the financial support, a large share of existing buildings is thermally refurbished	1
Energy Systems	All social groups participate/profit from the energy transition	1
	Financial benefits from long-term/future-oriented investments (e.g. by selling energy and/or reduced purchased energy)	1
	Price stability	1
	Socially fair energy pricing (financial savings for households)	1
	Turbocharging process thanks to reciprocal learning and intelligent linkages between different activities	1
Energy Systems	Improved quality of life	3

Mobility & Transport	Improved quality of life (e.g. through time savings)	1
Nature-based & Other innovative solutions	Improved quality of life, climate actions as a relaxing and rehabilitation area (greening measures) for all social groups	1
Mobility & Transport	More social equality (e-cars shared instead of purchased)	1
	Strong financial support at the beginning offers the possibilities of long-term costs reductions (e.g. economies of scale)	1
	Sustainable mobility & transport will become the new standard	1
Nature-based & Other innovative solutions	Large scale highly innovative climate actions implementation lead to an improvement of life (e.g. via a smart & intelligent city)	1
	Society is strongly connected to the climate measures and turbocharges the process	1

Table 5 Madrid B-1.1 Indicators

Field(s) of Action	Indicator(s) Used	Frequency
Buildings and Heating and Cooling	Awareness raising for new users (recruitment)	1
	Fostering the entrepreneurial and mediating skills of public employees as agents of change	1
	Increased citizen satisfaction by involving and accompanying them in the process of rehabilitating their home	2
	Increasing the comfort of new and future building stock	1
	Reducing the cost of energy bills	1
Electricity	Working groups, associations and social movements linked to the promotion of local energy communities for the expansion of renewable energy coproduction practices	1
Transport	Improved coordination of loading schedules and reduced loading times	1
	Increased possibilities to reconcile work with personal and family life	1
	Internal working group to strengthen internal governance	1
Electricity	Perception of the "proconsumer" role of citizens as being able to combine their position as passive energy consumers with that of active producers in the energy production chain	1
Transport	Positive perception of school users and their families about the management of the school and its environment	1
	Positive public perception of the city's public administration	1
	Public satisfaction with freight logistics management	1
Waste and reforestation	Positive perception of governance	1

Table 6 Mannheim B-1.1 Indicators

Field(s) of Action	Indicator(s) Used	Frequency
Economic	Business/technological innovation	1

	Congestion	1
	Decreased future maintenance & capital costs	1
	Disruption of energy, transport, water and communications networks	1
	Economic impact of disasters	1
	Increased economic returns of natural capital	1
	Increased economic thriving (quality of jobs, sustainable supply chains, etc.)	1
	Increased technological readiness & rate of adoption	1
	Increased visibility & knowledge/tech transfer for local businesses/ventures	1
	Labour conditions	1
	Labour productivity	1
	Local economic activity & global connectivity	1
	Mainstreaming of new economic models like proximity & sharing economy	1
Environmental	Biodiversity and ecosystem services	1
	Light pollution	1
	Resilience to climate change/adaptation	1
	Water/soil quality	1
Public Health	Disaster/disease/contamination-related health impacts	1
	Health costs	1
	Health impacts from extreme heat or cold weather	1
	Increased physical activity and active lifestyles	1
	Premature deaths	1
	Preparedness for health service delivery	1
Social	Transport poverty	1
	Food security	1
	Education and public awareness	1
	Energy poverty	1
	Water security	1
	Transparency and accountability	1
	Security/protection for poor/vulnerable populations	1
	Number of households and businesses forced from homes/places of work	1
Social Inclusion, Democracy & Cultural Impacts	Enhanced citizen & communities' participation & social capacities for participation/engagement	1
	Improved access to information, awareness & behavior change	1
	Increased access to job/employment and skill development opportunities	1
	Increased awareness of social issues	1

Table 7 Sønderborg B-1.1 Indicators

Field(s) of Action	Indicator(s) Used	Frequency
Built Environment	An energy efficient home has become the new normal when buying a house	1

	Higher rate of energy efficiency in buildings is achieved	1
	Larger part of the built environment is refurbished and less personal investments are needed	1
	Methods integrated in citizens way of thinking	1
	New generations grow up with a highly democratic and participatory mindset leading to better impact in the future	1
	Visionary long term leadership	1
Energy systems / Green infrastructures	Lower cost of energy (compared to no-action)	1
Energy systems / Green infrastructures	Improved quality of life	1
Mobility & Transport		
Mobility & Transport	Forming new policies with cross pressure support from EU	1
	Learning bridge the gap between the actions, ambitions and alignment of the goals	1
	New competencies and innovations	1
Waste & circular economy	Business development and development of utility companies and municipalities.	1
	Households finance the recycling and circular economy and reduction of Nitrous Oxide from wastewater due to local regulations.	1
	Improved wellbeing	1

Table 8 Stockholm B-1.1 Indicators

Field(s) of Action	Indicator(s) Used	Frequency
Built Environment	Reduced energy costs	1
Green infrastructure & nature-based solutions	Heat source from biochar production	1
	Improved climate adaptation	1
Mobility & Transport	Increased accessibility	1
	More space for pedestrians and green infrastructure	1
	Shorter travel times	1

Table 9 Valencia B-1.1 Indicators

Field(s) of Action	Indicator(s) Used	Frequency
Buildings and Heating	Improved air quality for emission reductions by proposing improvements over what is required by the technical code	1
Re-naturalization, Biodiversity, and Resilience	Improved climate resilience (temperature regulation, flood prevention, ...)	1
	Improved physical and mental health	1
Transport	Improved road safety with fewer cars on the road	2
	More health for people	1
Economy and Industry	Improved ecosystem health	2
Waste		
Economy and Industry	Improved water quality	3

Re-naturalization, Biodiversity, and Resilience Waste		
Buildings and Heating Electricity Re-naturalization, Biodiversity, and Resilience Transport Urbanism and Habitat	<u>Increase in property value</u> from urbanisation actions a) having parks and urban gardens close to the house b) the inclusion of green infrastructure c) more adapted and renovated buildings, with lower energy consumption	6
Buildings and Heating Electricity Re-naturalization, Biodiversity, and Resilience Transport Urbanism and Habitat Waste	<u>Just social transition that reduces inequalities</u> , by a) allowing improvements in thermal comfort and better conditions to cope with climatic risks such as heat waves, etc. b) allowing proximity of amenities, not linking safe and fast mobility to car ownership, also by promoting green infrastructure that enables adaptation to climate change and improved health c) enabling proximity of endowments d) reuse, etc. of the circular economy e) democratising the ecosystem services provided by Nature-Based Solutions f) proposing numerous measures to combat energy poverty	6
Transport Urbanism and Habitat	Improved well-being/socially, creation of social ties	3
	Recovery of public space for citizens, both that left by car parks, streets, etc.	2
	Saving time in the case of urban interventions in the city of proximity, by avoiding traffic jams, having closer facilities.	2

Table 10 Valladolid B-1.1 Indicators

Field(s) of Action	Indicator(s) Used	Frequency
Buildings and Heating	Increase in the value of housing (not monetised in the economic model)	2
Transport	Increased security	1
	Optimisation of public transport frequency	1
	Less traffic	1
	Reduced infrastructure maintenance	1
	Time saving	1
Waste	Improved water quality	1
	Ecosystem health	1

Table 11 Vitoria-Gasteiz B-1.1 Indicators

Field(s) of Action	Indicator(s) Used	Frequency
Buildings and Heating Energy	Encouraging public-private partnerships	3
Energy Transport Waste	Enhancing quality of life	38

OTHERS: Agri-food		
OTHERS: Industry		
Buildings and Heating Transport	Improved management of administration/administration relations	4
Waste	Promoting industrial ecology and the circular economy	4
OTHERS: Industry		
Energy	Promotion of energy self-sufficiency	7
OTHERS: Industry		
Energy Waste	Promotion of renewable energies for electricity generation	10
OTHERS: Industry		
Buildings and Heating Energy Waste	Reduction of energy bill expenditure	22
Buildings and Heating Energy	Reduction of light pollution	2
Buildings and Heating	Improvement of the thermal comfort of dwellings and buildings	7
	Increase in the value of buildings	4
	It appeases the possible reluctance of the public due to the necessary initial high-cost investments	1
	Promoting new technologies and forms of sustainable construction	1
	Promoting the renovation/refurbishment of the city's building stock	4
	Reduction of household expenditure on energy bills	2
	Renewal of the domestic appliances	1
Energy	Overcoming possible reluctance from the public due to necessary initial high-cost investments.	1
Forestry	Increase in the area of carbon sinks in the city	2
OTHERS: Agri-food	Improvement in the management of production processes	4
	Improvement in the organic production of agricultural and food products	3
	Promoting healthy and local food	1
	Promotion of food self-sufficiency	1
Transport	Enhancing multi-stakeholder and multi-level relationships	1
	Fostering social relationships	1
	Generation of real solutions to implement projects on innovation in logistics and mobility of goods and people	1
	Improving quality of life	1
	Improving universal and urban accessibility	5
	Optimisation of routes, distances and number of goods delivery journeys	2
	Promoting local mobility and shared mobility	2
	Promoting the use of public transport	7
	Reducing the number and distance of journeys	3

	Reduction in the number of journeys made in own vehicles	7
	Reduction of traffic and congestion	2
	Renewal of the municipal (goods delivery/logistics, bus, vehicle) fleet	6
Waste	Improved landfill management.	2
	Increase in the reuse of materials, decrease in the generation of urban/forestry waste.	3
	Reduction of landfill disposal and reduction of landfill investments.	3
	Technological innovation in the local industrial sector	1

Table 12 Zaragoza B-1.1 Indicators

Field(s) of Action	Indicator(s) Used	Frequency
Buildings and Heating Electricity	Greater democratisation of the energy sector	2
Transport	Fair distribution of public space	1
	Improved health associated with active mobility	1
	New economy around electric technologies	1
	Reduction of accidents	1
Other: Re-naturalization	Ecosystem services of green infrastructure	1

3.1 Co-benefit Indicators: Locally Developed/Not Present – Notes

All 354 indicators listed in Section 3.0 were mapped to the most relevant NZC framework domain (114) and subdomain (240) if it existed. The corresponding notes describing why the given indicator wasn't coded to close/exact alignment were deduped and summarized by domain in the tables that follow.

Table 13 Biodiversity

Subdomain/General	Notes
Ecological awareness	Doesn't cover the degree of public acceptance or increasing public engagement/participation Doesn't really cover civic education/outreach and raising public awareness Doesn't really deal with the mental and physical health aspects of increased/restored natural areas, etc.
Nature restoration	Soil, carbon sink/capture & other adaptation benefits not accounted for Congestion is only covered indirectly under "Digitalisation and Smart Urban Technology>Urban Data Platforms and Data Spaces"; blue/green corridors in relation to congestion not covered
General Notes	Increased economic returns of natural capital or NBS for example not covered Ecosystem services from natural restoration etc not covered General measure of tree canopy etc but doesn't specifically cover ecosystem services like stormwater reduction etc.

	Increased climate resilience/adaptation not covered Interconnection between NBS, etc. and water quality not covered
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Table 14 Digitalisation and Smart Urban Technology

Subdomain/General	Notes
Urban Data Platforms and Data Spaces	Measures number of users and end user satisfaction with platforms, but doesn't capture outcomes of usage like fostering local commitment and behavior change (5)
General Notes	Congestion only covered in relation to use of urban data platforms This domain doesn't equate digitalisation to improved quality of life

Table 15 Economy

Subdomain/General	Notes
Adoption of Key Technologies	Developing innovation skills for new innovations not covered Doesn't cover tech readiness to adopt the key technologies Measures % of deployment of key technologies (like electrification/charging infrastructure), not making transport by car more affordable
Economic thriving	GDP doesn't account for job quality, sustainable value chains etc
Local entrepreneurship & local businesses / ventures	Expansion/interconnection of ventures in global green markets for example not covered Mainstreaming new business models not measured, just no. of ventures
Number of skilled jobs & rate of employment	Just covers number of jobs, not access/skills development Doesn't cover skills and learning loops for instance with new sustainable housing approaches
General Notes	Doesn't cover innovation or innovation ecosystem growth, just number of climate-neutral startups & new biz ventures, etc. Partnerships to co-create/learn new methods/solutions between municipalities and utilities for example isn't covered

Table 16 Finance and Investment

Subdomain/General	Notes
Capital Efficiency	Covers emissions reduced to spend ratio, not renewable energy sales or energy savings Emission to capital spend measured, not cost savings from reduced maintenance etc.
Fiscal Responsibility	Not specifically long-term costs reductions (e.g. economies of scale)
General Notes	Cost recovery/lower energy bills related to increased investment in renewables not covered Doesn't cover blended finance or innovating financial instruments (2) Finance from households/regulations for recycling/circularity not covered Increasing funding via nat'l/int'l level policies not covered None of the subdomains cover attracting/blending finance

Public/ external investment in climate actions covered; spend in relation to specific actions like retrofit/refurbishment or NBS isn't covered (2)

Table 17 Greenhouse Gas Emissions (GHG)

Subdomain/General	Notes
Energy Generation	Cost reduction/cost recovery not really covered Intersection of NBS/biofuels and heating not covered Measures energy generation but not revenues from any potential energy surplus for example (2)
Grid-supplied energy (electricity, heat, steam or cooling)	Measures emissions and energy loss in system but doesn't cover reducing the unit cost of energy through upgrading infrastructure/powering with renewables (2)
Stationary Energy	Measures energy use in city boundary, not energy savings from installing energy efficient lighting for example (2) Measures energy use in city boundary; cost savings from making buildings more energy efficient with retrofits or with more developed regulation not covered; built environment optimization indirectly covered under "Digitalisation and Smart Urban Technology>Green ICT and Smart Metering" (18)
Transport and Mobility	Measures emissions from vehicles in city boundary; doesn't cover benefits of upgrading/electrification etc. (8) Optimization/travel times not covered; covered indirectly under "Digitalisation and Smart Urban Technology>Urban Data Platforms and Data Spaces"
General Notes	Enabling regulatory development for renewable energy/energy communities (1) or a green tax (1) not covered; similarly not really dealt with under policy support indicator: "Social Inclusion, Innovation, Democracy and Cultural Impact>City capacities for participation / engagement" (2)

Table 18 Public Health & Environment

Subdomain/General	Notes
Air quality	Deals with air quality measures not upgrading codes
Equitable & affordable access to housing	Doesn't measure reducing household energy bills through for example heating retrofit or upgrading appliances/lighting (5) Doesn't measure sustainability of housing or cover standard setting (3) Measures affordability of housing and % of households experiencing energy poverty, not % of housing stock renovated/retrofitted or lowering the cost of energy (3) Energy poverty only covered in relation to access to housing Social cohesion in relation to housing access not covered (or in the social inclusion domain) Lowering energy costs overall not covered, just lowering the number of households unable to afford energy costs

Liveability, attractiveness & aesthetics of the built environment	<p>Measures satisfaction with green and non-green public spaces, doesn't cover benefits of specific measures like energy efficiency (1), neighborhood revitalization/retention (1), safety (1), reduced pollution from landfill waste (2), repurposing spaces used for cars (2), benefits of agri-food measures like reducing emissions/healthier food (5), comfort/health from heating/cooling (7), improved services (13), or improved circularity (30) [62]</p> <p>Time savings due to urban interventions and proximity like 15 min city not covered</p> <p>Increasing the share of spaces for public use/green infrastructure not covered</p> <p>Doesn't measure equitable access to green spaces</p>
Physical and mental well being	<p>Only covers general overall wellbeing over course of Mission period via survey, specific urban/habitat interventions (1) or reducing commute times for work/life balance (1) not really covered (2)</p>
Road safety	<p>Covers deaths, not accident reduction or security of transport modes for example (4)</p> <p>The only indicator that deals with congestion "Digitalisation and Smart Urban Technology>Urban Data Platforms and Data Spaces" has to do with using smart solutions, doesn't cover other solutions like shared mobility or Uni/school outreach/partnerships etc. (6)</p>
General Notes	<p>Doesn't deal with improved health from greener/active travel</p> <p>Innovative energy systems in building stock and impact on comfort/quality of living not covered</p> <p>No coverage of NBS specific benefits or learning loops related to NBS/other innovations</p> <p>Only deaths due to road safety covered</p> <p>Resilience & adaptation not really covered directly anywhere, just indirectly under Biodiversity and "Liveability, attractiveness & aesthetics of the built environment>Green Spaces"</p> <p>Road safety is covered under this domain; not safety of public spaces</p> <p>Light pollution isn't covered under this domain (2)</p> <p>Water quality not covered under "Resource Efficiency>Water management" and soil quality not covered at all</p>

Table 19 Resource Efficiency

Subdomain/General	Notes
Deployment of material cycles & circular economy	<p>Mainstreaming/promoting new business models like industrial symbiosis not covered under this domain or under Economy domain (3)</p> <p>This category and "Economy>Adoption of Key Technologies" doesn't cover innovation capacity or innovating a sector for example with industrial symbiosis (integrated energy systems like hydrogen recovered from waste etc.)</p>
Sustainable and resilient food production	<p>Covers % of food produced locally and food waste volume, not quality of production processes (7)</p> <p>Doesn't cover food insecurity of households for example, just % local food production</p>

	Doesn't cover promotion of food security/self-sufficiency; the only policy support indicator is specific to SI: "Social Inclusion, Innovation, Democracy & Cultural Impact>City capacities for participation/engagement>Policy support for promoting climate neutrality"
Waste management and efficiency	Doesn't measure decrease in flows going to landfill or cover reducing costs of maintaining landfills (3) Ecosystem health via waste mgmt. interventions not covered (3)
Water management	Doesn't cover improving water quality, just compliance with wastewater directives (3) Security of water supply not measured
General Notes	Measures for recycling/circularity of materials, not reuse or reducing forestry/urban waste generated (3) Optimization, for example of freight, isn't covered; covered indirectly under "Digitalisation and Smart Urban Technology>Urban Data Platforms and Data Spaces" Reducing energy costs from various circularity measures not covered (5) Savings or reducing energy costs not covered

Table 20 Social Inclusion, Innovation, Democracy and Cultural Impact

Subdomain/General	Notes
Behaviour change towards low carbon lifestyle and practice	The only policy support indicator is specific to SI: "Social Inclusion, Innovation, Democracy and Cultural Impact>City capacities for participation / engagement>Policy support for promoting climate neutrality"; it measures the number of policies set up to promote climate neutrality, not specific sectoral interventions like increased local food production (1), local/shared mobility (2) housing/ construction standards (2), increased circularity/industrial symbiosis (3), active travel or green/public transport (9), energy (19), or comms/ outreach for increased engagement/uptake of interventions (36) Measures share of public/green transport modes, but not access (5) or patterns in other transport modes, like the reduction in single occupancy trips in cars (10) [15] Active travel/lifestyle (1) or affordability of green/public transport (1) not specifically covered (2) Benefits of behavior change like wellbeing/time savings/reduced congestion from green/public transport (3) or of pro-consumerism in terms of energy savings selling energy back to grid etc (1) not covered; quality of life measures only cover built environment/public spaces (4) Reduced congestion only covered under "Urban Data Platforms and Data Spaces" in digitalization category; use of smart urban tech for this isn't mentioned in CCC
Citizen & communities' participation	Measures % of open processes not assessing impact like approval of interventions, changing mindsets, etc. (2) Social capacities for (1) or profitability of (1) participation/engagement not measured (2)

City capacities for participation / engagement	Broad climate neutrality actions and only covers number of people involved; specifics like community energy, promotion/comms, or resulting learnings not measured Doesn't really cover legal frameworks, just number of policies Policy support only measures number of policies not public perception/acceptance (3)
Functioning of democratic institutions	Transparency and accountability of institutions not covered
Social cohesion, gender, equality & equity	Reduced inequality and improved resilience via retrofits not covered Wellbeing, social cohesion/ties and shared transport interconnection not covered
Social Innovation	Education/civic engagement programs to increase citizen involvement/advice to help citizens save on energy bills not covered Wellbeing aspects of social inclusion/empowerment not covered
Social justice	Democratization of ecosystem services of NBS not covered Doesn't cover access/proximity to greener/public transport modes Energy pricing only covered under access to housing New business models like sharing economy not covered; Climate-Neutral City Start-ups under Economy doesn't measure social inclusion Reducing inequalities and increasing resilience by proximity/access and green infrastructure not really covered
General Notes	SI domain only covers learning and capacity/skills for SI; org interventions/learning/relationship building/partnerships etc. to improve sectoral actions not covered (16) Acceptance/positive perception of governance not covered, just awareness Accessibility of green transport/active travel modes not covered Civic engagement/participatory mindset in current citizens and future generations not covered Leadership capabilities/visioning at any level of governance not covered Fuel poverty only covered under Public Health & Environment>Equitable & affordable access to housing; other energy poverty interventions from a social justice lens (e.g. energy sector wide) not covered Only no. of ppl involved; learning & standard setting not covered Org interventions like internal working groups (1) or partnerships/multistakeholder working groups (1) not covered; just SI areas (2) Reduced inequality via circular economy interventions not really covered Reducing transaction costs of implementation from policies, regulation, governance interventions or comms/outreach for standards/norm change not covered Satisfaction w/ specific services like retrofit not covered

3.2 Co-benefit Indicators: Too Generic for Subdomain Match

Indicators that didn't have enough corresponding information to match to a NZC Indicator Framework subdomain were coded to "too generic for subdomain match". Most had to do with health. There are detailed in the table below.

Table 21 Indicators without sufficient information to match to a subdomain

City	Field(s) of Action	Indicator(s) Used	Frequency
Mannheim	Economy	Costs	1
	Public Health	Mental wellbeing/quality of life	1
	Social	Mobility and access	1
	Economy	Revenue generation	1
Valencia	Built Environment	More health for people	5
	Energy Systems		
	Urbanism and Habitat		
Valladolid	Mobility & Transport	Improved health	1
Vitoria-Gasteiz	Mobility & Transport	Fostering social relationships	1
		Increased investment in recharging infrastructure	1
	Built Environment	Health improvement	51
	Energy Systems		
	Mobility & Transport		
	OTHERS: Agri-food		
OTHERS: Industry			
Waste & Circular Economy			

4.0 Recommendations

Indicator Refinements

The most frequently occurring gaps in the NZC indicator framework are given in the bullets below, with recommended refinements in blue. Analysis of subsequent mission label cohorts as well as indicators cities have developed as a part of their pilot projects will provide additional insights into what indicators cities are using in these and other areas. Overall there is a mismatch between the data architecture of the indicator framework (domains and subdomains) and the impact pathways (systemic levers and climate action fields) set out in the NZC theory of change. Finding ways to better link them so they are complementary will be helpful moving forward (likely leveraging existing cross theme MEL work underway and engaging platforms like Kausal and ClimateView).

Public Health & Environment

- Quality of Life – limited to satisfaction with public green/non-green spaces **Benefits resulting from interventions should be better accounted for (e.g., time savings, better health from active travel etc)**

Social Inclusion, Innovation, Democracy and Cultural Impact

- Policy support – limited to no. policies for climate neutrality RE: social innovation **Overall policy/regulatory/organizational interventions should ideally be captured in a category like “Institutional and Governance Innovation & Enabling Infrastructure”**
- Citizen/Stakeholder Engagement/Communications – subdomains covering this only capture number of people/processes (and limited to SI) **Measures should better capture internal vs external engagement mechanisms and depth/breadth/duration of engagement**

Energy Cost Reductions/Energy Savings

- This came up a lot and seems to be spread across “Finance and Investment>Fiscal Responsibility” (RE: recovering costs from e.g. energy generation), “Public Health & Environment>Equitable & affordable access to housing” (RE: lower household energy costs), and “GHG>Stationary Energy” & “Digitalisation>Green ICT” (RE: energy savings from things like retrofits) **Measures should better capture income generation and cost savings from sectoral interventions and lowering energy costs (e.g. for households)**

The indicator framework needs to better reflect locally developed indicators that are emerging, in terms of capturing the most useful/crosscutting indicators and standardizing them; however, to do this, meta-data on the actual units of measure used etc. needs to be obtained/analysed. At present, the indicators are not standardized (lots of permutations of the same indicators/compound indicators) and most are not backed up with specific units of measurement, so it is impossible to verify the veracity of the indicators or if cities are committed to tracking them over time.

Indicator Processes & Learning

The initial analysis of the CCCs in terms of monitoring & evaluation tools and processes revealed that cities included very limited information on local MRV processes or how process and co-benefit indicators are being refined/fed back into planning/actions. More detailed information on this needs to be drawn out in the iterations. Finding ways (via Excel templates or other tools) to identify which indicators are helpful and which can be dropped/refined to provide better evidence will support a more streamlined MRV process. Too many indicators in various places (CCC, project spreadsheets, etc) and a lack of a way to visualize/centralize/report on these indicators risks them staying tied to grant reporting cycles and not being mainstreamed. It's also clear that city mission staff need more training on the difference between indicators and tactics/outcomes etc.; this is particularly the case with the social innovation/organisational intervention indicators and the indicators listed in Section 3.2.

APPENDIX A – W1 Monitoring and Evaluation Tools & Indicators

Monitoring and Evaluation Tools & Indicators – Window 1 Mission Label Cities

City	Monitoring Tools & Inputs	Indicator Process	Indicators	Monitoring & Evaluation Refinement	Review Periodicity	Cases Studies
Cluj-Napoca	NZ local coalition and NZC Champs campaign + university partner digital monitoring tools + Climate Neutrality Digital Twin	Sustainable Energy and Climate Action Plan 2022-2030 (SECAP) + Integrated Urban Development Strategy (IUDS)	Indicators in the Buildings; Transport; Waste; industrial processes and product use (IPPU); and livestock, land, and aggregate sources/ nonCO2 emission sources on land (AFOLU) sectors	Energy Manager following Action Plan Guide + collaborative work with Coalition/universities to consolidate monitoring system	City level reporting not specified; Biennial (expectation for CCC but also not specified)	
Klagenfurt	Primarily reporting and a Climate relevance tool to raise awareness/ assess the climate impacts of City Senate proposals	Driven by iterations of its Smart City Strategy + external expert	Primarily focused on the following action fields: energy systems, mobility & transport, built environment & housing, and nature-based & other innovative solutions	Input from Smart City Lab stakeholders and external expert reviewer	Annually (reports to City Senate); GHG monitoring (every 2 years)	
Madrid	'e-Mission' tool for advanced diagnosis, simulation and evaluation of GHG emission source scenarios in the city + digital twins for demonstrators	2022 updated Roadmap to 2050 + Madrid 360 strategy pre-Label, integrated with Material Economics model	Primarily Buildings & Heating/Cooling; Transport, electricity, and waste and reforestation	To be defined with participating Spanish cities through the development of a monitoring and evaluation plan; tied to City Accord process amongst 7 Spanish cities (national platform, citiES2030)	Annually (GHG emissions pathways report); Biennial (CCC)	
Mannheim	ClimateView monitoring dashboard; the Local Green Deal Platform; a monitoring and evaluation tool developed in CoLAB (NZC pilot project) for non-technical measures	SECAP process tailored to CCC criteria and situated within the LGD framework "iDEAL for Mannheim"	Top measures defined across 8 action fields: 1) municipal administration; 2) private households; 3) mobility; 4)	The Climate, Nature and Environment Department monitors/updates the KSAP with input from transition team, LGD managers, and stakeholders/ citizens; Climate View Monitoring linked to developing iteration of	Annual reporting on CO2 balances, activities, and target progression; CCC updates/reporting via CDP &	Pilot Local Green Deal (LGD) city: hybrid LGD-CCC model

	leading to climate neutral/emission reducing actions		commerce, trade, services; 5) industry; 6) energy production; 7) green-blue infrastructure; and, 8) land use.	investment plan for all action areas; work; further develop indicators specific to LGDs, e.g., private/citizen contributions to CO2 reductions	MyCovenant every 2 years	
Sonderborg	Masterplan tool for tracking indicators developed under Masterplan2029; CenterDenmark (CDK) Energymap/data-platform	Based on Masterplan2029 and DK2020 plan	Primarily buildings, transport, and waste; both industrial processes and product use (IPPU) and livestock, land, and aggregate sources/nonCO2 emission sources on land (AFOLU) sectors are mentioned as insignificant	ProjectZero public-private partnership (PPP) supporting Masterplan2029, including progressing KPIs, aligning stakeholders, and monitoring/reporting	ProjectZero PPP annual reports on Masterplan 2029 KPI-progression and results; DK2020 & CCC - every 2 years by municipality	
Stockholm	An excel tool for portfolio analyses (in collab. w/ KTH); digital citizen panel; Sensible Stockholm Lab	Driven by the City Environment Program	Primarily Buildings; Transport; Waste; industrial processes and product use (IPPU); and livestock, land, and aggregate sources/nonCO2 emission sources on land (AFOLU) sectors	Revisions are tied to City budget, follow environmental monitoring program criteria, and are reported via the integrated management system (ILS) & CDP	Annually (reports via ILS); Every 2nd year (updated CAP, etc)	
Valencia	Energy One-Stop Shops; Global Platform for (tourist) destination management and intelligence; creative city & culture storytelling; Mission alliance/TT; Urban forum -external engagement; Col-lab - public accelerator for social/urban innovation startups; City-University	València 2030 Climate Mission (compliance w/ int'l policy frameworks + EU Green deal) + 2030 Urban Strategy integrated with SECAP 2019 inventory and	key sectors (Buildings and heating, Transport, Waste, Electricity/ Industrial processes and use of waste products; AFOLU + additional impact domains of Urbanism & Habitat, Economy & Industry, and Renaturalization	To be defined with participating Spanish cities through the development of a monitoring and evaluation plan; tied to City Accord process amongst 7 Spanish cities (national platform, citiES2030)	Regular review of action plan via City plenary sessions; Mission Alliance/city review of CCC every 2 years	Pilot EEA synergies between mitigation & adaptation missions

	Binomials (R&I, knowledge, dialogue, collab); Ciuta-lab citizen lab; climate assembly	Material Economics model	Biodiversity & Resilience to be addressed in future iteration			
Valladolid	Digital tools for measuring impacts of transport policies (Next4Mob); public mobility scenarios (SPINE); urban delivery/route planning; building retrofits (RehaVIVA 2.0, Valladolid Solar); CIRCULAR labs self-assessment tool	2022 Roadmap, Valladolid Urban Agenda 2030, and other key local strategies/policies; integrated w/ SECAP 2030 emissions inventory and Material Economics model	Primarily Transport, Buildings & Heating, electricity, and waste (circular economy & nature-based actions/solutions)	To be defined with participating Spanish cities through the development of a monitoring and evaluation plan; tied to City Accord process amongst 7 Spanish cities (national platform, citiES2030)	City level internal review in one year; Biennial review of (CCC)	
Vitoria-Gasteiz	Use, extension and adaptation of GIS + SmartEnCity digital neighborhood model to create digital twin; Agirre Lehendakari Center social innovation tools (inputs on needs, impacts, evolving evaluation)	SECAP 2030 + Urban 2030 Agenda starting point for CCC combined with Material Economics model; SECAP is 2 interrelated strategies - Integrated Energy Transition Action Plan (PATEI) + Climate Change Adaptation Action Plan (PAACC)	Primarily transport, buildings and heating, waste, industrial processes and product use (IPPU), and agriculture, forestry and land use sectors	To be defined with participating Spanish cities through the development of a monitoring and evaluation plan; tied to City Accord process amongst 7 Spanish cities (national platform, citiES2030)	Annual final energy consumption & GHG inventories + annual CCC plenary; Biennial review of (CCC)	Highlighted as best practice for MEL in terms of Impact Pathways connection w/ Actions & Indicators (Table B-3.1, p 154): See D1.5 , p 17, Lessons learned from Window 1
Zaragoza	Open Government Platform; Idea Zaragoza tool	2022 Roadmap pre-Label, integrated with Zaragoza Zero Emissions 2030 activities + SECAP 2030 and Material Economics model	Primarily transport, buildings and heating, electricity, waste, and other - renaturalization and circular economy	To be defined with participating Spanish cities through the development of a monitoring and evaluation plan; tied to City Accord process amongst 7 Spanish cities (national platform, citiES2030)	City level reporting not specified; Biennial (CCC)	

APPENDIX B – W1 Mission Label Cities Co-benefits Factsheet Draft

The First 10 Mission Label Cities: How They Measure the Co-benefits of Climate and Innovation Actions

SUMMARY

The first 10 cities awarded the EU Mission Label developed their Climate City Contracts (CCCs)² before the publication of the NetZeroCities Indicator Framework in March 2024. The Indicator Framework³ describes a set of required (measuring direct benefits, i.e., impact on GHG emissions) and recommended (measuring the co-benefits, i.e., indirect impact) indicators for monitoring the impact of CCCs. To support understanding how cities are incorporating co-benefits indicators in their CCCs and facilitate future improvements to impact evaluation, this factsheet describes the co-benefits indicators used by the first cohort of Mission Label Cities.

Table 1 First 10 cities awarded the Mission Label on 12 October 2023⁴

City/Cities	Country
Klagenfurt	Austria
Sønderborg	Denmark
Mannheim	Germany
Cluj-Napoca	Romania
Madrid, Valencia, Valladolid, Vitoria-Gasteiz and Zaragoza	Spain
Stockholm	Sweden

WHAT IS THE MISSION LABEL?

The Mission Label is the European Commission's recognition of cities' successful development of their Climate City Contracts (CCCs), which outline the overall vision for climate neutrality and contain an action plan as well as an investment strategy.

CO-BENEFITS SELECTED BY CITIES

As a part of the Climate City Contract development process, cities need to link local actions (across domains of emissions and sectors) for climate neutrality with their indirect positive impacts on other areas and sectors, i.e. with their co-benefits. The selection of these co-benefits is mapped for each field of action in each city's Climate Action Plan, according to the action field classification outlined in the NZC Theory of Change⁵: Built Environment; Energy Systems; Mobility & Transport; Waste & Circular Economy; Green Infrastructure & Nature-based Solutions; and Others as relevant. Cities were given flexibility in terms of how the climate actions were structured in the Action Plans and which indicators

² <https://netzerocities.app/ClimateTransitionMap>

³ Documentation: <https://netzerocities.app/resource-4120>; Spreadsheet: <https://netzerocities.app/resource-4156>

⁴ European Commission. (2023, October 12). Ten European cities awarded with EU Mission Label for their plans to reach climate-neutrality by 2030. European Commission Press Corner. Retrieved May 14, 2024, from https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/ip_23_4879

⁵ See available resources materials: <https://netzerocities.app/resource-4249>

were selected. Most cities, with the exception Mannheim, mapped their selected co-benefits indicators by the suggested action fields. The data and how the action fields were structured are given below:

- Half of the cities included some indicator metadata, that is, specific units of measurement and descriptions of the co-benefits indicators
- Action Field 1: Built Environment – 4 cities adopted this category, 4 used Buildings and Heating, 1 used Buildings and Heating and Cooling, 1 didn't include this category
- Action Field 2: Energy Systems – 3 cities conformed to this domain, 1 added Green infrastructures, 4 used Electricity, 1 used Energy, 1 didn't include this category
- Action Field 3: Mobility & Transport – 4 cities conformed to this domain, 5 simply used Transport, 1 didn't include this category
- Action Field 4: Waste & Circular Economy – 3 cities combined this with Waste, 4 simply used Waste, 1 used Waste and reforestation, 2 cities didn't use this category
- Action Field 5: Green infrastructure & nature-based solutions – 2 cities adopted this category; 1 city used Nature-based & Other innovative solutions; 1 used Re-naturalization, Biodiversity, and Resilience; 1 used Forestry; 4 didn't include this category
- Action Field 6: Others as relevant⁶ – Vitoria-Gasteiz conformed to this, adding *OTHERS: Agri-food* and *OTHERS: Industry*; Valencia added *Economy and Industry* and *Urbanism and Habitat* as action fields
- Although all the other cities chose to cover them separately in Section C of their Climate Action Plan according to its design, Cluj-Napoca added *Organisational and Governance Innovation* and *Social and Other Innovation* as action fields
- Mannheim used the Economic, Social, Public Health, and Environmental categories appearing in their expression of interest (EOI), combined with the categories of Economic Development Impacts; Public Health & Environmental Impacts; and Social Inclusion, Democracy & Cultural Impacts. The following were combined for ease of analysis: Economic with Economic Development Impacts; Social with Social Inclusion, Democracy & Cultural Impacts; and Public Health and Environmental with Public Health & Environmental Impacts.

The recommended (voluntary) co-benefit indicators that cities linked to their climate actions were concentrated in section B of the CCC. Those selected for organizational, governance, and social innovation interventions (enabling actions) were detailed in section C, but apart from Cluj-Napoca, cities did not structure these according to the NZC Theory of Change. Thus, this factsheet maps section B indicators against the NZC Indicator Framework, the high-level categories of which are outlined below in Table 2. The section C indicator types are then described, along with highlights of interventions and the co-benefits they are designed to achieve.

Table 2 NZC Indicator Framework – Recommended (voluntary) indicator high-level categories

NZC Indicator Framework – Indicator Categories (Recommended)
Biodiversity
Digitalisation and Smart Urban Technology
Economy
Finance and Investment
Greenhouse Gas Emissions (GHG)

⁶ Combined these with the others/added categories used by Valencia and Vitoria-Gasteiz, along with those used by Mannheim as they differed from the action fields used by the other cities.

Public Health & Environment

Resource Efficiency

Social Inclusion, Innovation, Democracy and Cultural Impact

Overall, the cities selected 712 indicators in association with the actions outlined under the fields of climate action, the distribution is given below in Figure 1.

Figure 1 All co-benefit indicator categories by fields of climate action

CO-BENEFIT INDICATORS BY CLIMATE ACTION FIELD

Figure 2 Action Field 1: Built Environment

Figure 3 Action Field 2: Energy Systems

Figure 4 Action Field 3: Mobility & Transport

Figure 5 Action Field 4: Waste & Circular Economy

Figure 6 Action Field 5: Green infrastructure & Nature-based Solutions

Figure 7: Action Field 6 - Others as Relevant

CO-BENEFIT INDICATORS BY INNOVATION INTERVENTIONS

The cities selected 175 indicators linked to organisational and governance innovation as well as social innovation interventions, the distribution is given below in Figure 8.

Figure 8 Co-benefit indicators by innovation interventions

INNOVATION INTERVENTION CO-BENEFITS: HIGHLIGHTS

Cluj-Napoca

- Organisational and Governance Innovation – leveraging new ways of governing condominiums to reduce energy bills/emissions and employing an interactive digital platform to foster local buy-in and behaviour change
- Social Innovation – using a NetZeroCaravan in neighbourhoods and suburbs and a Civic Imagination & Innovation Centre to improve local awareness and understanding of climate neutrality objectives

Klagenfurt

- Organisational and Governance Innovation – a Climate relevance tool to raise awareness/assess the climate impacts of City Senate proposals
- Social Innovation – a Smart City Lab to evaluate climate action project ideas from local stakeholders and a corresponding Climatefund to financially support small-scale climate actions initiated by citizens

Madrid

- Organisational and Governance Innovation – Interdepartmental Climate Group to mainstream the climate dimension across municipal actions and the Collaborative Platform for Climate Neutrality in Spanish Cities (citiES 2030) to design and implement simultaneous actions in several Spanish cities
- Social Innovation – Madrid Zero Emissions open events and Madrid City Studio and Municipal School Environments (collaboration and outreach programmes) to disseminate information and involve citizens, schools, and universities in experimentation and co-designing solutions

Mannheim

- Organisational and Governance Innovation – the iDEAL for Mannheim online platform to initiate, activate and bundle concrete sustainability agreements with citizens and stakeholders and a participatory budget to fund winning ideas
- Social Innovation – wider public participation events like the Urban Thinkers Campus, tailored citizen engagement mechanisms like the Citizens' Council "Climate Protection 2030", and the NetZeroCities CoLAB-Committed to Local Climate Action Building⁷ Pilot project, all building awareness of climate issues and building local commitment for change

Sønderborg

- Organisational and Governance Innovation – restructuring of departments in support of the ProjectZero Masterplan2029, a ProjectZero public-private partnership, and a Masterplan tool for tracking indicators, all to increase participation, political support, transparency, and competencies
- Social Innovation – a city strategic plan for citizen engagement - along with supporting plans for energy, heating, and personal transport - to foster social inclusion, awareness/learning, improved wellbeing, and better link plans with social outcomes

Stockholm

- Organisational and Governance Innovation – collaboration with other Swedish cities to support climate neutral cities and a good life for all through the Viable Cities platform and The Electrification Pact for an emission-free inner city
- Social Innovation – the Sensible Stockholm Lab collaboration to investigate new dimensions of a smart city (like public health and governance models) and a digital citizen panel to collect input and develop ways to engage citizens, with a focus on young people and lowering the barriers to a climate-positive life for vulnerable groups

Valencia

- Organisational and Governance Innovation – the Mission Day by Mission Team, an open space for operational management of the Climate Mission; Mission-driven Public Procurement of Innovation (PPI) programme to develop mission-oriented PPI projects and a corresponding Mission Public-Private Investment Fund
- Social Innovation – the Urban Forum, a space for debate and reflection on the development of the city model defined in the València 2030 Urban Strategy; a Climate Assembly; and a Ciuta-lab (citizen laboratory at Las Naves), all working toward extending the concepts of citizen science and climate co-creation and deliberation on climate justice criteria. Valencia also has a dedicated communications strategy focused on attracting citizens to the Climate Mission by explaining co-benefits and improvements in the city.

Valladolid

- Organisational and Governance Innovation – SMARTVA Intelligent Data Platform!, a smart platform for more efficient public management and decision-making translating into improved delivery of innovative public services; strengthening and aligning departments and the innovative city ecosystem, driven by the main orchestrator of the mission team, the Innovation and Economic Development Agency

⁷ <https://netzerocities.eu/germanys-pilot-activity-colab-committed-to-local-climate-action-building/>

- Social Innovation – the Local Mission Platform, spaces for co-creation and stakeholder involvement, and an Innovation and Sustainability Hub are all designed to generate new forms of collaboration with all city stakeholders who will work towards climate neutrality in the city. University-City Binomials will deliver mission-oriented research that is then scaled up.

Vitoria-Gasteiz

- Organisational and Governance Innovation – a multi-level platform / multi-stakeholder space to facilitate multi-stakeholder collaboration and share information on climate neutrality and climate change issues, supported by an overarching Mission Communication Strategy; Ensanche 21: Vitoria-Gasteiz Renovation Society, a former urban expansion agency refocused on coordinating Mission objectives at the neighbourhood level, improved relations within the administration, and fostering greater proximity to citizens
- Social Innovation – the Vitoria-Gasteiz living lab, increasing the city's innovation capacity through public-private collaboration (to help companies with innovative technological products or circular economy solutions) and promote implementation of experiments in real environments in the city

Zaragoza

- Organisational and Governance Innovation – the Open Government Platform and the Idea Zaragoza tool to promote improved data governance and re-use of information by citizens, businesses and other organisations for new business and value-added services
- Social Innovation – use of social tools (like education, awareness raising, training, and climate participation) for climate empowerment to create and encourage a social culture of climate neutrality and improve public health, including measures to address fuel poverty (like an energy advice point); the Zaragoza Activa platform for fostering new initiatives from local companies committed to climate neutrality